

Project:
ISABEL
 (Grand Agreement 691752)

"Triggering Sustainable Biogas Energy Communities through Social Innovation"

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Societal Challenge: "Secure, clean and efficient energy"

D3.1: ISABEL on-line portal, crowdsourcing tools and mobile apps

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

Main authors

- ✓ Mr Iakovos Delioglanis (Q-PLAN project team)
- ✓ Mr Ioannis Kostopoulos (White Research project team)

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1. Introduction

The current document provides an overview of the initial version of the fully operational ISABEL project portal structure, general provisions that guided its development and the operational procedures that are applied at the beginning of the project. It should be noted that the partners will closely monitor its usage in order to update its structure according to the project activities and end-users' feedback and increase its attractiveness, while emphasis is given to "cross-referencing" so as information is accessible from multiple pages/sections. Therefore, this initial version of the portal will evolve further as the project activities matures.

The web portal has been launched in March 2016 (<http://www.isabel-project.eu>) aiming to act as:

- ✓ **A dissemination and communication tool**, informing biogas stakeholders at regional and national level (e.g. biomass providers, biogas producers, energy providers, policy-makers and public authorities, technology providers, consultants, cooperatives, energy consumers, etc.) on:
 - ⇒ The project objectives, activities, workplan, contact points (i.e. partners) and findings;
 - ⇒ The basic concepts that set the framework of the project implementation, namely Biogas production and consumption, Community Energy and Social Innovation;
 - ⇒ The biogas sector in the 3 targeted countries (Germany, UK and Greece);
 - ⇒ Relevant initiatives at regional, national and European level that foster the development of the biogas as well as the broader Renewable Energy sectors (e.g. FP7/H2020 projects, regional bottom-up initiatives, national/international organisations, etc.); and
 - ⇒ Relevant reports, studies and events.

- ✓ **An entry point to the project Social Media pages** (Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter).

- ✓ **A support platform** for the regional Biogas Communities hosting a variety of on-line tools adjusted to the regional stakeholders' needs:
 - ⇒ Facilitating internal communication and collaboration of the Communities' members
 - ⇒ Enabling them to share ideas and concerns on local/regional interventions to promote Community Biogas concept and strengthen the sector in general.

Important note: during the first phase of the project, the partners focused on *understanding* the regional specificities in terms of analysing the regional biogas sector and the local communities' perception on biogas, namely their interests, thoughts and concerns around biogas putting emphasis on their societal and environmental dimensions. Therefore, our first target was to increase visibility of the project create a point of reference for the future project activities. The various on-line support tools will be developed in the coming period in close collaboration with the regional Communities so as to address their specific collaboration needs.

Welcome to the Horizon 2020 ISABEL project website

The ISABEL project aims to foster the concept of **community biogas** and lead the way for its market take-up based on a vision that includes three core interacting elements: (i) local production & consumption, (ii) community involvement, and (iii) sustainable biogas. As such, the project's proposal can be summarized in the following three statements:

- 1 It promotes **local production-consumption** systems of waste-based (ie sustainable) biogas.
- 2 It assumes that a local and inclusive (**community-based**) **governance model** would be appropriate for the sustainable functioning of such a system
- 3 It argues that under such conditions **biogas can be viewed as a public good** rather than a commodity

Overview

ISABEL is about promoting, supporting and developing community biogas in Europe. The project is set on providing all the framework conditions for biogas communities to shape, develop and thrive and works on all angles in order to take full advantage of the societal benefits of local community-driven biogas systems, fuelled and inspired by social innovation principles.

Objectives

In order to realise its vision, ISABEL sets specific objectives that will eventually ensure the expansion of its core notions and approaches and the replication of its outcomes to other European regions.

Concept

ISABEL integrates the notions of Social innovation, Community Energy and Biogas in order to foster the development of Biogas Community Energy projects and support their uptake and enlargement. The project puts forth a simple concept by revolving around these pillars and unfolds through their application in 3 different European contexts.

News

ISABEL News Centre provides an overview of current project news as well as the most recent news that revolve around the biogas and community energy world.

Events

Throughout the ISABEL project lifetime a wide range of events will be organised in order to exchange with our stakeholders and communicate the ISABEL concept, approach and results.

Regions

Germany, UK, Greece

Get Involved

Get In Touch

Newsletter

SUBSCRIBE

Stay Tuned

European Commission

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[Sitemap](#)

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Figure 1: ISABEL web-portal home page (www.isabel-project.eu)

2. General provisions

2.1 Language

The content of the final web portal as well as the on-line support tools that will be hosted will be in the national languages of the 3 targeted regions (English, German and Greek). Meanwhile, any material (e.g. report, legislation, etc.) that will be in a language other than English will be properly marked.

It should be noted that the current first version of the portal is only in English following the overall strategy of its development (i.e. in-line with the project objectives for the first phase). The multilingual content will be available in autumn 2016 to support the partners' effort to build/strengthen regional biogas communities.

2.2 Operational procedures

Partners' role

- ✓ **Q-PLAN** is overall responsible for the design, technical development and maintenance of the web portal and the on-line collaboration tools and will act as the *administrator* carrying out any structural improvements to enhance its practicability and attractiveness.
- ✓ **White Research (WR)**, as the project Dissemination Manager is overall responsible for:
 - ⇒ creating and updating the portal content and its presentation (e.g. graphical outlook and usability of the portal, content 'visibility', etc.).
 - ⇒ 'marketing' activities to enhance the visibility of the portal ensuring that it is highly ranked in on-line search engines.
 - ⇒ quality control of the information that is published on the portal
 - ⇒ monitoring the partners' performance to ensure that the targets are met and suggest corrective actions if and when necessary.
- ✓ **All partners** will contribute to the portal content and periodically send articles/material regarding the biogas sector in their regions, relevant regional/international events, information on Community Energy initiatives, etc. to WR to be published on the web portal.

Content Management and rights

- ✓ The portal consists of two discrete access controlled areas:
 - ⇒ **a public area** where any visitor can get information regarding the project results and activities as well as the Communities' general activities; and
 - ⇒ **a private area**, where only the project partners will have access acting as an *internal repository*
- ✓ Q-PLAN (as portal administrator) is able to change both the structure and content of the portal ad-hoc.
- ✓ All content will be visible to all visitors.
- ✓ Site visits, statistics and other information on visitors' views (e.g. number of pages per visit, time on site, most viewed pages, etc.) is measured using Google Analytics, while a counter is being used to measure the number of downloads per document.

2.3 Technical considerations

- ✓ Special provisions were made so that both the content and structure (creation of sub-categories/sections) of the portal can be updated on demand by the administrator (Q-PLAN).
- ✓ Advanced Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) techniques are engaged to enhance the site visibility in search engines.
- ✓ The content management system allows an unlimited number of pages/articles to be created/posted, while an integrated text editor similar to Word (Tiny MCE) enables the editor to use similar to Word formatting choices and add images, videos, etc. as well as create photo galleries or document libraries.
- ✓ The entire portal is periodically backed up to limit the loss of information.
- ✓ The content management system is using smarty PHP template engine to create web pages' template(s) and it runs in any software that has PHP and MySQL installed.
- ✓ The portal is in-line with the Web 2.0 paradigm and fully responsive providing an optimal viewing and interaction experience across multiple devices.
- ✓ The portal supports multilingual content enabling the addition of information in several languages.

3. Web portal overall structure

Sitemap

Pages

- About
 - Activities
 - Empowering
 - Supporting
 - Understanding
 - Overview
 - Community Biogas and ISABEL
 - Objectives
 - Partners
 - Work plan
- Blog
- Coming soon
- Concept
 - Biogas
 - Community Energy
 - Germany
 - Greece
 - Social Innovation
 - UK
- Contact us
- Get Involved
- News centre
- Portfolio
- Relative links
 - Organisations
 - EU organisations
 - Regional organisations
 - Relevant initiatives
 - EU-funded bioenergy projects
 - EU-funded similar projects
 - Regional initiatives
 - Renewables and biogas
 - Initiatives focusing on Biogas
 - Initiatives focusing on Renewable Energy Sources (RES)
- Triggering Sustainable Biogas Communities Through Social Innovation
- Useful material
- Sitemap

Figure 2: ISABEL web portal map

4. Screen shots

Figure 3: “About” section

Figure 4: “About” → “project partners” section

Figure 5: "Concept" section

Figure 6: "News centre" section

The screenshot displays the 'Relative links' section of the ISABEL portal. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'About', 'Concept', 'News centre', 'Relative links', 'Useful material', and 'Partners' Area'. The main content area is titled 'Relative links' and contains a list of categories: 'Relevant initiatives', 'EU-funded similar projects', 'Regional initiatives', 'EU-funded bioenergy projects', 'Organisations', 'EU organisations', and 'Regional organisations'. Below this list, several project cards are shown, each with a title, a brief description, and a 'Read more' link. The cards include 'Community Power', 'Biogas landscape and specificities in the 3 targeted regions', 'Biogas Barometer 2014 by EurObserv'ER', and 'EU Renewables Report, June 2015'. A red arrow points from the 'EU-funded similar projects' category to the 'Community Power' card. Another red arrow points from the 'Regional initiatives' category to the 'Biogas landscape and specificities in the 3 targeted regions' card. A third red arrow points from the 'EU-funded bioenergy projects' category to the 'Biogas Barometer 2014 by EurObserv'ER' card. A fourth red arrow points from the 'EU organisations' category to the 'EU Renewables Report, June 2015' card.

Figure 7: "Relative links" section

The screenshot displays the 'Useful material' section of the ISABEL portal. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'About', 'Concept', 'News centre', 'Relative links', 'Useful material', and 'Partners' Area'. The main content area is titled 'Useful material' and contains a list of reports and documents. The reports include 'Renewables 2016 Global Status Report', 'Biogas landscape and specificities in the 3 targeted regions' report', 'Social Innovation and Community Energy best practices, methods and tools across Europe' report', 'Biogas Barometer 2014 by EurObserv'ER', and 'EU Renewables Report, June 2015'. A red arrow points from the 'Biogas landscape and specificities in the 3 targeted regions' report' category to a detailed view of the report. The detailed view shows the report title, a brief description, and a 'Read more' link. The report title is 'Biogas landscape and specificities in the 3 targeted regions' report'. The brief description states: 'The report "Biogas landscape and specificities in the 3 targeted regions" analyses the regional biogas landscape and specificities in the 3 targeted regions in terms of (i) the existing biogas production and supply chains (farmers/breeders/foragers, biogas producers, intermediaries, energy consumers and local/regional authorities), (ii) their operational practices and impact (economic & social), and (iii) the best practice approaches in Europe.' The 'Read more' link is highlighted in green.

Figure 8: "Useful material" section

The screenshot shows the web interface of the ISABEL repository. The browser address bar displays 'isabel-project.eu/repository/'. The page title is 'eXtplorer' and it includes a search bar and navigation icons. The current mode is 'extplorer' with a 'Logout' link, and a note suggests switching to 'ftp' mode. The main content area shows a directory tree on the left and a detailed directory listing on the right. The directory listing table is as follows:

Name	Size	Type	Modified	Perms	Owner
Data_Management	4 KB	Directory	2016/04/28 16:17	775 (rwxrwxr-x)	n/a
Deliverables	4 KB	Directory	2016/06/08 10:26	775 (rwxrwxr-x)	n/a
Grant_Agreement_documents	4 KB	Directory	2016/03/17 10:19	775 (rwxrwxr-x)	n/a
Project_management	4 KB	Directory	2016/04/28 16:19	775 (rwxrwxr-x)	n/a
Project_meetings	4 KB	Directory	2016/03/17 10:32	775 (rwxrwxr-x)	n/a
Publicity	4 KB	Directory	2016/06/27 11:30	775 (rwxrwxr-x)	n/a
SI-CE_and_regional_biogas_landscape	4 KB	Directory	2016/03/17 11:52	775 (rwxrwxr-x)	n/a
Telco	4 KB	Directory	2016/06/21 12:48	775 (rwxrwxr-x)	n/a

Figure 9: “Partners’ area” section